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RENEWABLE AND NON-RENEWABLE HC DEPOSITS

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Abstract

Gradually, there is an accumulation of facts (replenishment of reserves of long-exploited deposits, inconsistency of the oil field exploitation period, pulsating flow rates), which indicate contemporary oil and gas formation and replenishment of initial reserves with incoming new portions of hydrocarbons. Established facts of the replenishment of oil and gas reserves in the fields under development, along with other noted evidence, indicate that the processes of generation, migration of oil and gas and formation (reformation) of deposits occur much faster than previously thought - within several years, and sometimes even in a matter of months. This paper will focus on the following: the main features and stages of formation of replenished deposits, the location of oil and gas basins with renewable deposits, the principles of resource potential assessment, and approaches to the development of such hydrocarbon systems.

Keywords: HC generation zone, hydrocarbons, replenishment of hydrocarbon deposits, reservoir pressure, source rock, HC shale, phasing of formation, DHI, abnormally high reservoir pressure (AHRP), potential balance method, cyclic development.

Introduction

At the turn of the 21st century, a hypothesis was born about the renewable resources of hydrocarbon deposits of oil and gas, which is rapidly gaining momentum and arousing great interest among representatives of the oil and gas sector. However, the majority of experts say that the process of replenishment of hydrocarbon deposits takes tens of thousands of years but a considerable portion of experts hold a different point of view: the processes of migration and formation (or reformation) of deposits occur much faster, over several years, and sometimes even in a matter of months and weeks, depending on the proximity to the source of HC generation [4].

The most obvious and representative examples of such a phenomenon are the HC deposits of Tatarstan, Western Siberia, Chechnya, Azerbaijan, Iran, Qatar, the USA, Vietnam, the western and southern coastal parts of the Caspian Depression (Russia and Kazakhstan) and the Indolo-Kuban trough (Russia). These deposits are characterized by the fact that at the late stages of development, when reserves (including geological ones) were almost exhausted, hydrocarbon production continued, while the annual volumes of extracted fluids remained unchanged for many decades. For example, in some small deposits of the North Caucasus, Azerbaijan and Central Asia, production has been carried out since the end of the XIX century to the present. The famous Romashkinskoye field in Tatarstan has been intensively developed for more than half a century, as a result of which a much larger amount (+ 7BB1) of oil was extracted from the depths than was estimated during the appraisal of the field.

There are also numerous examples of "revived wells" that were conserved due to high watercut, and

resumed production after several years of downtime. Thus, the high rate wells of the Tersko-Sunzhensky district (Chechen Republic), drilled back in 1893, became widely known. For almost half a century of intensive development, the wells were heavily flooded, and in 1941 many of them had to be conserved. The wells did not work during the entire war period, and after 1945 they were deconserved and production recovered. It turned out that almost all previously highly watered wells began to produce clear oil, as a result of the fact that in 4 years of downtime, deposits were reformed and the volume of the deposit was restored. Another example is the Kudinovskoye field, located in the Volgograd region – so, in August 2009, the torch burned for about a week at the well No. 320, which had been worked out for a long time. It turned out that there were accumulations of condensate in the formation, which manifested itself with the start of welding work at the well, which led to the fire.

Similar events occurred at the Zykh and Govsany fields in Azerbaijan in the southeastern part of the Absheron peninsula. Over the long years of development, starting in 1935, oil production at the fields has significantly decreased, but a large volume of gas condensate is still being extracted, and the pressure in the wells does not drop. The reserves of the deposits have already been recalculated twice, but exact figures have not been received now (the current RF is about 90%). Most likely, the process of migration and replenishment of deposits with new portions of gas condensate occurs due to nearby mud volcanoes. There are similar fields on the Azerbaijani shelf of the Caspian Sea, for example, such well-known deposits as Shah Deniz and Azeri-Chirag-Guneshli.

In the Grozny oil basin, there are Oktyabrskoye, Tashkalinskoye and Oisungurskoye fields, which have been developed for more than 60 years. In the Krasnodar area, the duration of active development of some deposits is up to 56 years (Zybza-Glubokiy Yar) [20].

Some deposits of India and the USA complement the list of long-lived deposits. Thus, oil production in India at the Digboi field in Assam began in 1890 and continues to this day. There are about 100 deposits in the USA with a development period of more than 70 years (for example, the development of the East Texas field began in 1930 and continues at the present time) [10].

The observed phenomena in the old deposits have been noted for a long time. Gradually, there is an accumulation of facts (replenishment of reserves of long-exploited deposits, inconsistency of the oil field exploitation period, pulsating flow rates), which indicate contemporary oil and gas formation and replenishment of initial reserves with incoming new portions of hydrocarbons.

Currently, it is becoming obvious that many hydrocarbon deposits are a complex and constantly operating hydrodynamic system capable of self-healing in a relatively short time, measured in years and even months, depending on the proximity to the source of generation. The development and exploitation of deposits disrupts the dynamic equilibrium in the reservoir, stimulating a natural influx of hydrocarbons, which begin to compensate for production.

Thus, the development of renewable hydrocarbon deposits must be planned based on a scientifically sound balance generation volumes (potential balance [4, 5, 15, 18]) and possible flow rates during the operation of deposits based on the replenishment rate.

In his famous work "Antifragility. How to benefit from chaos" [25] Nassim Taleb identified two main systems on a planetary scale – fragile and antifragile. Antifragility is not a synonym for stability, but rather a sign of constant improvement and self-improvement with an ever-increasing impact, unlike fragile systems that collapse even with small impacts by the "domino" principle. In relation to HC systems, it is also possible to distinguish fragile (located far from generation sources and having lost hydrodynamic connection with them as a result of tectonic processes) and antifragile (using the potential of nearby large HC generation sources during production).

Signs of sites with renewable hydrocarbon resources.

Given the expected depletion of non-renewable reserves in the near future, it is important to concentrate oil and gas exploration activities on the analysis and exploration of highly prospective regions with renewable hydrocarbon reserves as soon as possible.

First, it is important to understand what Exploration criteria for replenished deposits. The accumulated experience of working with such deposits indicates that the field's ability to replenish hydrocarbons depends on several important factors:

- The presence of abnormally high reservoir pressure (AHRP);

- Richness of source rock organic matter (TOC>2%) and its significant volumes (SR area of more than a thousand km² and a SR formation thickness of 100 m) and catagenetic maturity (the presence of source rocks in the oil and gas generation zones);

- The proximity of the deposit to the source of generation (or the presence of a regional slope of source rocks);

- The presence of hydrocarbon migration routes (associated with salt diapirism, faults or mud volcanoes) connecting oil and gas source deposits and a trap.

As secondary signs of the process of modern hydrocarbon inflow, the following can be indicated:

- "revived" wells where production was resumed after several years of downtime due to their high water content and reduced reservoir pressure;

- The discrepancy between the duration of the field's operation and estimated reserves (oil RF is greater than 0.7);

- pulsating flow rates;

- Observation of a rapid trend in reservoir pressure recovery as a result of a decrease in the volume of hydrocarbon extraction (as a result of workovers or replacement of equipment);

- Reduction of oil density in the area of hydrocarbon intake;

- An increase in the methane content in the HC intake area;

- increased content of helium and hydrogen in gas condensate deposits;

- Increasing of condensate density and condensate content in deposits depending on the depth;

- Increasing of gas factor depending on the depth;

- Reduction of reservoir water mineralization because of mixing of reservoir and organogenic water in HC intake area.

The stage of formation of deposits with replenished hydrocarbon resources.

According to the concept [4, 5, 15, 18], developed on the example of the Jurassic-Cretaceous system of the territory of the Middle Caspian Sea, the formation of deposits of various phase states occurs continuously and at the genetic level, the total effect of this process is divided into two main enlarged stages:

1. The first is the oil and gas stage (formation of deposits),

2. The second stage is the gas condensate stage (re-formation of deposits).

At the first stage, as a result of the full reaching of the source rock potential in the main oil formation zone, mainly oil and oil-and-gas fields are formed along numerous migration routes. At the second stage, the fate of oil deposits depends on their location: within or outside the migration routes of hydrocarbon gases. If the structural plan along the migration routes has not changed over time, then the process of replenishment (renewal) of the oil and oil and gas deposits formed at the first stage continues at the next gas condensate stage.

The gas condensate stage begins with a violation of the hydrodynamic equilibrium of the reservoir system with the beginning of oil production. The generated condensate, due to the pressure difference, begins to

flow into the formations under development in the form of jet streams, and after a certain time the field turns from oil to gas condensate. In the event that the oil traps at the second stage turn out to be away from the migration routes, the connection with the generation zone is interrupted, and as a result, the deposit falls into the category of deposits with irreplaceable reserves. At the same time, non-hydrocarbon gases (mainly CO₂ and H₂S) begin to penetrate into the higher horizons from the most submerged kitchen deposits, and the increased content of helium and hydrogen in the gas condensate deposit indicates a modern influx of gases from below, mainly due to faults.

The process of converting an oil deposit into a gas condensate one has been studied most fully on the example of the Kizilovsky and Cherepetsky horizons of the Alekseevsky field located on the western side of the Caspian depression (Fig.1). The new gas condensate stage of the field is associated with the unique resources of the generation zone under conditions of AHRP. The presence of a regional salt cap rock ensures the preservation of deposits and the maintenance of AHRP in the entire subsalt rocks volume. In this regard, the inflow of hydrocarbon gases is accompanied by an increasing of the reservoir pressure in the deposits, rather than a drop, as usually occurs during the production.

At the Alekseevsky field, the initial reservoir pressure (before production) was 48.43-49.95 MPa [8]. During the development process, an uncharacteristic slow drop of reservoir pressure was observed. When

the oil in the field was sufficiently extracted and the average reservoir pressure decreased to 19 MPa (the transition stage from oil to hydrocarbon gas), instead of the expected further decrease, on the contrary, it tended to increase to the initial reservoir pressure - 48.85 MPa, and then sharply increased to 53...58 MPa (gas condensate stage) and the influx of gas condensate began (Fig.1).

Another example of two-phase ongoing generation of hydrocarbons is the renewal of deposits at the Romashkinskoye field, where more than 140 wells, previously considered unprofitable, were restarted for production [19]. They showed the flow of light carbonated oil (in front of a general oil density increasing, which is common during the long-term deposit development) [21].

It is generally believed that the lightest oil in the deposits is confined to the arches, and density of the fluid increases on the wings. However, at the Romashkinskoye field, oil on the steep wing of the deposit adjacent to the fault has a reduced density and viscosity (0.854 g/cm³ and 2.2 MPa·c) compared to the arch (0.860 g/cm³ and 2.4 MPa·c), the gas factor is 71 m³/t and the bubble pressure is 94 MPa [3]. It is also characteristic that the formation temperature on the considered wing of the deposit is 1-2 °C higher. Obviously, this is a direct sign of the ongoing oil inflow from the oil-producing Upper Devonian domanic kitchen along the faults.

Figure 1. – Initial condition (1.1) and the transforming (1.2) of oil deposit into gas-condensate one of Alekseev field (kizilian and cherepetian horizons) as a result of the production: 1.1 – equilibrium oil-gas condition (before production); 1.2 – equilibrium changing after the start of oil production; MZGG – surface of fault displacement; AHRP – abnormally high reservoir pressure in Alekseevskaya-2 well of Alekseevskoe field (1.3), as an example of transforming oil deposit to gas-condensate one [8].

Observations at the fields of Western Siberia (Verkhnekolik-Yeganskoye, Severo-Gubkinskoye) showed a change in the composition of oils from well to well [19]. It is noted that oil samples from wells located in the disturbance zone have a lower density and a higher yield of gasoline fractions, which is explained by the modern influx of hydrocarbons through faults and disturbances from the Upper Jurassic Bazhenov kitchen formation.

New observations and rethinking of accumulated facts show that the processes of migration and formation (or reformation) of deposits occur quite quickly, over several years, months and even weeks [4]. Thus, experiments performed in the Tersk-Sunzha region have established that the speed of vertical oil migration reaches hundreds of meters per year, or 1-2 meters per day [22].

These and other data indicate that the movement of the hydrocarbon fluid occurs at a much higher rate than previously assumed, the rate of formation is estimated not in millions of years, but in years and months, the process of formation and reformation of hydrocarbon deposits is ongoing and continues at the present time.

The fundamental factor of the intensive hydrocarbon generation process presence is the quality of the oil and gas source rock. The exchange process occurs especially quickly (months and weeks) where the generation zone is located in close proximity to the reservoir

rocks (literally tens to hundreds of meters away). In the Azerbaijani Shah Deniz field, the kitchen stratum is the Oligocene-Lower Miocene clay deposits of the Maikop formation with a very high oil generation potential (TOC up to 15%), lying 1-1.5 km below the uppermost target and underlay the last productive target [6] (Fig.3).

The distance of up to 1.5 kilometers from the source rock to the uppermost target in this case is not critical, since another important factor of the delivery of new portions of HC to the targets is a permeable channel that plays the role of reservoirs "recharge" - mud volcanoes. Than closer the deposit to the HC generation zone, the faster the processes of its replenishment go. The presence of faults is a necessary condition for migration and the entry of new portions of hydrocarbons into the deposit. The processes of deposit replenishment will be more clearly observed in the immediate vicinity of a permeable channel (fault or mud volcano). Thus, in the Shah Deniz field, the processes of modern hydrocarbon migration are most obvious near the northern volcano.

In the case of the Karachaganak field in the Caspian basin, the source rocks located tens of kilometers from the field, which constrains the inflow of hydrocarbon volume necessary to maintain reservoir pressure (Fig.4). Hence, the expected moderate (compared to the Shah Deniz field) trend of reservoir pressure recovery at the field [7].

Figure 3. Geological cross-section of Pre-Caspian depression [7]

Thus, the presence of an active and closely interacting generation and accumulation system is the key to the presence of a deposit with replenishable hydrocarbon reserves.

The main role in the process under consideration belongs to the source rock (quality and potential). It is the primary source of the ongoing active processes of generation and migration of hydrocarbon fluid.

More than 90% of the world's initial recoverable oil and gas reserves were generated by the source rocks of six stratigraphic intervals:

- Silurian (9% of the world's reserves were generated),
- Upper Devonian-Tournaisian (8% of reserves),
- Upper Carboniferous – Lower Permian (8% of reserves),
- Upper Jurassic (25% of reserves),
- Medium Crataceus (29% of reserves)
- Oligocene-Miocene (12.5% of reserves).

The concentration of the main source rocks in these several stratigraphic intervals demonstrates the uneven distribution of source rocks over time. Consequently, their formation is not the result of a single process, because the distribution area, sedimentation features, as well as the geochemical characteristics of the source rocks vary from one time interval to another. The main factors that controlled the areal distribution of the source rocks, their geochemical type and OM are the paleolith of sedimentary areas, structural forms and the evolution of biota.

The source rocks of the Silurian, Upper Devonian-Tournaisian, Upper Jurassic and Middle Cretaceous were deposited during transgressive stages. Sedimentation of the source rocks of the Upper Carboniferous–Lower Permian and Oligocene-Miocene, on the contrary, occurred during periods of marine regression. A favorable combination of a number of factors - tectonic, climatic, hydrological and biological are a result of the formation of powerful, organic-rich source rocks of six main intervals, which contribute to the ongoing processes of active generation and migration of hydrocarbons.

The main oil and gas basins with replenishable hydrocarbon deposits

So, all hydrocarbon deposits can be conditionally divided into two groups: the first - deposits with replenishable reserves (fast, medium and slow-replenished) and the second - with non-replenishable reserves. In rapidly replenished deposits, the inflow of hydrocarbons can be expected within a few weeks up to 4 months, in medium-replenished deposits — within 4-24 months, in slow-replenished deposits - within 2-10 years.

A significant number of deposits belong to the category of non-replenishable or slowly replenishable. This happens if the deposits have been outside the hydrocarbon migration routes for a long time, or have been cut off from generation sources as a result of tectonic processes, or the deposits are located near small sized generation sources.

An example of non-renewable deposits: Venezuelan deposits of the Orinoco River belt [12], heavy oil fields of Alberta (Canada), Yareg field (Russia), heavy oil fields of Tampico-Misantla (Mexico), Tengiz, Northern Buzachi (Kazakhstan), Rumeila (Iraq), Rabeh East (Egypt), Caspian, Zapadno-Rakushechnoye, Khvalynskoye (Middle Caspian), Cantarelle (Mexico), Baobab (Cote d'Ivoire), Baleine (Cote d'Ivoire) and many other deposits in various regions of the world (Table 1).

Currently known deposits with renewable HC reserves are located within the following oil and gas basins, characterized by thick and organic-rich source rocks: Volga-Ural, Caspian, Middle Caspian, West Siberian, Azov-Kuban, North Sakhalin (Russia), South Caspian (Azerbaijan), Kulong (Vietnam), Santos Campos (Brazil), Benguela and Kwanzaa (Angola, Congo), Persian Gulf (Qatar, Iran, Iraq), Essequibo (Guyana), GOM (USA, Texas), Salino del Istmo (Mexico), northern slope of Alaska (USA/Canada), Mozambique (Mozambique, Madagascar) and Guinea (Nigeria) bays and some others (Fig. 4, Table 2-3).

Table 1.

Examples of fields with non-renewable HC reserves

Fields	Fields examples	Country/ province	Oil-and-gas Basin
Non-renewable HC deposits	Asphaltenes	Trinidad and Tobago	Orinoco
	Orinoco oil belt	Venezuela/ Orinoco river	Orinoco
	Bemolanga	Madagascar/ Bemolanga	Madagascar
	Altamira, Panuco, Ebano	Mexico/ Tampico	Tampico
	Cantarel	Mexico/ South GOM Offshore	Reforma Akkal
	Khvalynskoe	Russia / Middle Caspian	Middle Caspian
	West Rakushechnoe	Russia / Middle Caspian	Middle Caspian
	Caspian	Russia / Middle Caspian	Middle Caspian
	Alberta heavy oil fields	Canada	West Canadian
	Baobab	Kott-di-Vuar/ Deep offshore	Guinea Gulf Basin
	Tengiz	Russia / Near Caspian	Near Caspian
	Yaregskoe	Russia/ Komi Republic	Timano-Petchorian
	North Buzachi	Kazakhstan	North Usturt
	Rabeh East	Egypt	Esh El Mallaha
	Changuleh	Iran	Mesopotamian
Rumeila	Iraqe	Mesopotamian	

Figure 4. The main oil and gas basins of the world with the observed phenomenon of HC renewability in traditional reservoirs (1) with the location of the main fields with the observed phenomenon (4), in the basins with the shale formations (2) and basins where the SR is simultaneously shale deposits (3).

Table 2.

Examples of fields with renewable HC reserves

	Fields Exaples	Country/ province	Oil-n-gas Basin	№ on Fig. 4	HC Kitchen	TOC, %
Renewable HC deposits	Ur, Korchagin	Russia/ Middle Caspian sea	Middle Caspian	I	Low-Middle Jurassic	4-6
	V. Filanovsky	Russia/ Middle Caspian sea				
	Sarmatskoe	Russia/ Middle Caspian sea				
	Oktyabrskoe, Starogroznskoe	Chechnya / South-east of Near Caucasus	Tersky Caspian	II	Maikop, Low-Middle Jurassic	0,12-5
	Alekseevskoe, Malyshevskoe etc	Russia / Volgograd region	Near Caspian	III	Low-Middle Devonian	
	Karachaganak	Kazhstan / Near Caspian region			South Caspian	IV
	Shah-Deniz	Azerbaijan / Caspian sea				
	Azeri-Chirag	Azerbaijan / Caspian sea				
	Zykh, Gowsany	Azerbaijan / Southeastern part of the Absheron Peninsula	Volga-Uralsky	V	Domanic (Upper Devonian)	5-20
	South Neprikovskoe, Nikosko-Spiridonoskoe, Sofinskoe etc.	Russia/ Samara region				
	Romashkinskoe	Russia/ Tatarstan	West Siberian	VI	Bazhen (Upper Jurassic)	1-15
	Verkhnekolik-Eganskoe, Ust-Balykskoe, North Gubkinskoe	Russia/ West Sibir				
	Zyba-Deep Yar, Maikopskoe	Russia/ Krasnodar region	Azov Cubanian	VII	Maikop (Oligicene-Low Miocene)	1-3
	Ghawar, Khurais, Abqaiq	Saudi Arabia / Eastern Part	Persian Gulf Basin	VIII	Qusaiba (Low Silurian)	3-16,6
	Northern/ South Pars	Qatar-Iran / Central part of Persian Gulf				
	Kirkuk, Jumbur	Irque / Kirkuk				
	Libra, Guara, Tupi	Brasil / East part of Brasil offshore	Santos, Campos	IX	Lagoa Feia Group (Low Cretaceous)	4-9
	Kizomba, Marimba, Girassol, Jasmin, Nkala, Litchendjili	West Africa / Angola, Congo	Benguela, Kwanza	X	Bucomazi Fm (Low Cretaceous)	5-20
	Jubilee, Bonga, Forcados, Pennigton, Bras River	West Africa/ Ghana, Nigeria	Guinea Gulf Basin	XI	Albian and Senomanian black shales (Middle Cretaceous) / Takoradi (Middle-Upper Devonian) / Awgu, Araromi (Upper Cretaceous), Imo (Paleocene-Eocene)	>10 / 4 / 2-5
	Bach Ho (White Tiger)	Vietnam / South China sea ofshore	Cuu Long	XII	Upper Oligicene	1-10
	Sakhalin-I, II, III, Kurinskoe	East Russia / Okhotskoe sea	North Sakhalin	XIII	Upper Oligicene-Low Miocene	1-5
	East Texas	CIIIA/ Texac	Texas	XIV	Low Cretaceous	3-14
	Offshore GOM fields	USA/ North ofshore of GOM	North GOM	XV	Low Cretaceous	3-14
	Spraberry	USA/ West Texas	Permian	XVI	Upper Permian	5-8
	Pradho Bay	USA/ Alyaska	Northern slope of Alaska	XVII	Permian	4.5-15.5
	Zama, Yoti, Chinwol	Mexico/ South ofshore of GOM	Salino-del-Istmo	XVIII	Titianian	3-12
Liza, Payara etc	Guyana /East Guyana ofshore	Essecibo	XIX	Upper Jurassic	2-11	
Lagosta, Tubarao	Mozambique/ Mozambique ofshore	Mozambican	XX	Upper Jurassic and Low Cretaceous	2-10	

Table 3.

Main shale formations with the active process of HC generation

	Country	Oil-n-gas Basin	№ on Fig. 4	Formation	Age	TOC, %
Shale Formations	Australlia	Beetaloo	1	M. Velkerri	Pre Cambrian	4
		Canning	2	Goldwyer	Middle Ordovician	3
		Cooper	3	Roseneath-Epsilon-Murteree	Permian	3
		Georgina	4	L. Arthur Shale	Middle Cambrian	5.5
		Maryborough	5	Goodwood/Cherwell	Cretaceous	2
		Perth	6	Carynginia Kockatea	Upper Permian Low Triassic	4 5.6
	Argentina	Neuquen Basin	7	Vaca Muerta	U.Jurassic - L.Cretaceous	5
	China	Jiangan	8	Niutitang/Shuijintuo	Low Cambrian	6.6
		Junggar	9	Pingdiquan/Lucaogou	Permian	5
				Triassic	Triassic	4
		Sichuan	10	Qiongzhusi	Low Cambrian	3
				Longmaxi	Low Silurian	3.2
				Permian	Permian	4
		Songliao	11	Qingshankou	Cretaceous	4
		South China	12	L. Cambrian	Low Cambrian	3
	L. Silurian			Low Silurian	3.2	
	Subei	13	Mufushan	Low Cambrian	2.1	
	Tarim	14	Ketuer	Low Triassic	3	
	Mexico	Burgos	15	Eagle Ford	Middle-Upper Cretaceous	5
		Sabinas	16	Eagle Ford	Middle-Upper Cretaceous	5
		Tampico	17	Pimienta	Jurassic	3
		Veracruz	18	Maltrata	Upper Cretaceous	3
	Russia	West Siberian	19	Bazhen	U.Jurassic - L.Cretaceous	1-15
		Volga-Uralsky	20	Domanic	Upper Devonian	5-20
	USA*	Anadarko	21	Woodford	Upper Devonian	1-14
		Williston	22	Bakken	Devon-Low Carboniferous	1-35
Western Gulf		23	Eagle Ford	Upper Cretaceous	2-12	
Appalachian		24	Marcellus	Middle Devonian	2-14	
Denver-Julesburg		25	Niobrara	Upper Cretaceous	2-8	
Permian		26	Cline-Wolfberry-Wolfcamp	Upper Carboniferous	1-8	

When talking about high-quality source rocks that contribute to the renewable hydrocarbon resources, it is also necessary to keep in mind shale formations, where the phenomenon of renewable development will be observed even more clearly, since the newly formed fluid will flow directly into the well, avoiding losses during migration. In this case, the only obstacle is the choice of the most suitable development system, which will require drilling more wells and performing multi-stage fracking in order to maintain the required size of cracks in the formation, and, accordingly, the well flow rate.

The main basins with shale formations are the basins of the USA, Russia, Australia, Argentina, China and Mexico.

Approaches to reserves estimation with renewable hydrocarbon resources.

It is obvious that when assessing the HIIP of replenished hydrocarbon deposits, the use of the volumetric method is incorrect, since the dynamics of the inflow of hydrocarbons into the deposit (the presence of an active generation and accumulation permanent system) is not taken into account. The material balance method based on the dynamics of pressure drop will also not work - in such fields, since the pressure drops during the wells production, but when the well is stopped, the pressure begins to rise.

A predictive assessment of the initial geological resources of these deposits is possible by the volumetric genetic method [4, 5, 6, 7, 23], taking into account the total volume of the SR, TOC, type of generated HC, rock density, the parameter of HC output from the rock and the HC emigration coefficient.

Let us consider as an example the stage-by-stage calculation of the potential of the Maikop formation within the Shah Deniz field, recognized as the main SR within the South Caspian basin [4].

1) First, it is necessary to analyze the properties of the SR within the deposit (composition, TOC, thermobaric conditions, gradation of catagenesis).

The studied formation of the Oligocene-Lower Miocene age consists of dark gray mudstones. The Maikop formation is characterized by a high temperature gradient (4 °C/100 m) and enters the oil generation zone already at depths of 2000 m, within the field it is located in the zone of HC gases generation. According to laboratory studies, the formation is characterized by a high content of TOC, which varies from 0.07 to 15.1% (for calculations, we take the average value of this parameter equal to 7%).

2) The next important point is to determine the area of the SR involved in the HC generation.

Since reservoir formations within the Shah Deniz field lie directly above the SR of Maikop, the following approach was applied to determine the area of the SR involved in the HC generation: an area of 1 km was increased to the area of the studied field along the widest water contact.

The thickness of the Maikop formation can reach 2000 m for the Shah Deniz deposit. Let's assume that not the entire thickness of the Maikop formation is involved in the HC generation, but only the upper part of formation, about 500 m. In order to take this assump-

tion into account, the authors propose to use a coefficient of HC emigration equal to 0.25 (2000/4=500m→0.25)

3) As a result, it's possible to calculate the potential of the source rock using the formula:

$Q = S * H * \rho_{rock} * TOC * HC_{yield}$ [4], where

S [m²] is the area of the SR involved in the HC generation for a specific deposit or field

H [m] is the thickness of the SR

prock [t/m³] - density of the SR

Corg [%] - potential TOC content in the SR

HC yield [m³/t] - the amount of HC output from the SR

Taking into account the above parameters, the potential of the Maikop formation within the Shah Deniz field was calculated, according to which at least one cycle of reserve renewal at the field can be expected due to active generation processes and favorable HC migration routes from the underlying deposits of the powerful Maikop formation.

Determination of the replenishment of HC deposits of prospects at the Exploration and Appraisal stages

Based on the understanding of the fact that hydrocarbon resources are replenished, it is necessary already at the stages of Exploration and Appraisal to determine prospects according to the degree of possible deposits HC renewability with new HC volumes from oil and gas SR according to the following criteria:

1. Quick-to-refill (weeks):

1.1 Location of deposits near the SR (mainly vertical migration along faults, salt walls or mud volcanoes)

1.2 TOC of the SR >2%

1.3 High AHRP – >1.3

1.4 High gas content

2. Average-to refill (months):

2.1 Remoteness from the SR (mainly lateral migration)

2.2 Average AHRP – 1.1-1.3

2.3 Average gas content

3. Slow-to-refill (months-years):

3.1 Significant distance from the SR (lateral migration only)

3.2 Low AHRP – less than 1.1

3.3 Low gas content

Based on the above criteria, already at the Exploration stage, it is possible to determine the type of expected HC deposits and prepare appropriate recommendations for further development. For this purpose, it is necessary to carry out long-term pilot production (8-18 months) from the Exploration and Appraisal wells with periodic well shutdowns (4 stops, starting from 4 weeks and sequentially up to 1 week) to obtain the dynamics of reservoir pressure recovery [6, 7] and calculate the most optimal flow rate of production wells, taking into account the possible (permanent) deposits renewability by new HC portions.

For example, for the oil and gas basin of the Gulf of Guinea, prospects associated with the paleodelta of the Niger River can be assigned with a high degree of probability to the Quick-to-refill group (confined to

mini-basins with vertical HC migration), while turbidite Turonian prospects of the western part of the Gulf of Guinea (Ghana, Cote de Voire) belong to **Slow-to-refill group** or even non-replenishable (long-range HC migration from deep parts of the basin, reservoir pressures are close to hydrostatic).

Pliocene-Miocene prospects of turbidite genesis of the oil and gas basins of the Northern (South Texas subbasin) and Southern (Salino del Istmo subbasin) offshore of the Gulf of Mexico are highly likely to be rapidly replenished due to the proximity of prospects and fields to mini-basins with vertical migration from the Tithonian SR (TOC - 4-12%). The AHPR in the already discovered fields of both basins for Pliocene-Miocene deposits varies between 1.2-1.7, which indicates a high HC renewability potential.

Thus, at the Exploration stage, the analysis of the HC deposits replenishment of prospects based on regional data (basin modeling) and data by the first Exploration and Appraisal wells (including pilot production) will allow Operators to choose the most optimal approaches for further Production and maximize IRR and NPV.

Development of fields with renewable hydrocarbon resources

1) Traditional HC

In order to identify a field with replenishable reserves, it is necessary to analyze the dynamic of reservoir pressure and well flow rate during production. The nature of the rapid recovery of reservoir pressure in the deposits is an indicator of the processes of additional fluid intake.

Analysis of reservoir pressure for producing wells at the Shah Deniz field showed that all of them have the

same rapid tendency to restore reservoir pressure as a result of decreasing of fluid volume (Fig. 5). This fact suggests the presence of a powerful source of hydrocarbon deposits replenishment from the source of the constant HC generation. There are 3 mud volcanoes acting as a HC "supplier" for Shah Deniz deposits. As a result, there is a periodic HC replenishment over short periods of time.

The analysis of reservoir pressure at the Karachaganak field (Fig. 6) showed that during the 4 years of active development of oil deposit at moderate daily rates in the period from 2004 to 2008, the reservoir pressure decreased by only 5 MPa [7] (depletion angle of 5 degrees) (Fig. 6), which directly indicates the presence of some additional source of reservoir pressure maintenance. At the same time, during the considered period of time, almost no artificial reservoir pressure maintenance system was used (gas injection to maintain reservoir pressure was started in mid-2003, but was interrupted from November 2003 to June 2004 to carry out additional works at the production facility).

This tendency of weak dynamics of reservoir pressure drop is generally not typical for the same type of carbonate reservoirs. Thus, at the Tengiz field, there is a significantly faster decreasing of reservoir pressure (an almost linear trend with a fixed pressure drop angle of 23°) (Fig.7). During the first 4 years of Tengiz development (1998-2002), reservoir pressure decreased by 12 MPa (Fig.7), while at the Karachaganak field at comparable production rates, it decreased by only 5 MPa over the same period of time (Fig.6). The above difference may indicate that the intensity of HC intake from the SR is approximately twice as high at the Karachaganak field compared to the Tengiz field.

Figure 5. Formation pressure and daily gas rate dynamic by SDA-01,02,03z,04,05 wells of shah-Deniz field [6].

The closer the field is to the generation zone, the more likely the processes of reservoir pressure recovery are during the production. For example, at the Shah Deniz gas-condensate field, reservoir pressure recovery occurs in a matter of months, since productive formations lie directly within the generation zone (in its upper part) of the Maikop formation with a very high HC generation potential. For the Karachaganak gas-condensate field, the main volume of the SR is shifted to the center of the Pre-Caspian depression. The step-wise (lateral-vertical) type of jet migration of hydrocarbon gases in this case does not provide the inflow of

such a HC volume necessary to maintain reservoir pressure at any rate of production at this field. Hence, the moderate trend of reservoir pressure recovery in the field. Based on this, the main recommendation for the Karachaganak field, along with maintaining reservoir pressure, may be to regulate the production rate of producing wells to obtain a visible effect of natural replenishment of the field (for example, for the Karachaganak field, such an optimal production rate may be 15-16 Km^3/day , which will ensure a trend of reservoir pressure drop at a level of no more than 5 degrees) (fig. 6).

Figure 6. Reservoir pressure dynamics at the Karachaganak field (Object III) [7]

Figure 7. Reservoir pressure dynamics at the Tengiz field [7]

2) *Unconventional HC*

Conventional HC deposits are formed when fluids generated from the SR migrate into the reservoir formation, where they are trapped by an overlying caprocks. However, many of the generated hydrocarbons remain in the SR. Oil and gas extracted directly from the SR are usually referred to as "unconventional" hydrocarbons. Thus, there is no difference between traditional and non-traditional hydrocarbons, the only difference is the location of oil and gas, as well as the methods necessary to produce them. For example, formations that were previously considered only the SR have recently increasingly become "shale formations", some of which are already being produced, while the rest are in the active stage of resources evaluating [5, 9, 10, 11, 26, 27].

The famous Eagle Ford shale in south Texas in the USA is composed of mudstones, which are the SR, and at the same time an independent reservoir from which oil, light oil, condensate, and dry gas can be extracted, which simply never left the SR. The areas of greatest interest in the gas-condensate window area are those where the condensate content exceeds 50 g/m³. Further development of such areas will not depend on the current gas price, as it will be based on the production of liquid hydrocarbons, while it should be noted that the gas may have a high index of a wide fraction of light hydrocarbons (Natural Gas Liquids) and thus may bring additional profit to condensate production.

The development of shale deposits requires drilling of horizontal wells using various modifications of hydraulic fracturing technology. In horizontal wells with multi-section fracking, the yield of hydrocarbons can be several times greater due to greater coverage than in vertical wells without fracking [5].

All shale deposits can be developed for a long time, guided by the principle of cyclic development (Fig.8), which does not require the special costs [5]. The existing experience in the development of oil fields from the Maikop clay shales of the Batalpashin and Khadum formations of the Central and Eastern Precaucasia shows that after reservoir pressure drops and production rates decrease to a minimum, wells must be

preserved for a time sufficient to restore reservoir pressure [9]. After pressure compensation and the well re-run after downtime, the oil flow rates are restored (sometimes to the initial ones). Thus, there is a periodic self-replenishment of hydrocarbon reserves in the zones of active gas and oil generation.

To restore the initial production rate of oil/gas of shale formations, it is necessary to stop the well for 2.5-3.5 months (using the example of the Eagle Ford formation). This method of development can be represented as the equation: $(36+3)*N$, where 36 are the months of operation and 3 are the months of well shut-down, N is the number of cycles of replenishment of HC deposits depending on the TOC content (calculated by the potential balance method) [4, 5, 10, 11, 12, 14, 15, 18] (fig. 8).

Currently, companies engaged in shale HC production, in order to maintain a high level of production, are forced to continuously drill new wells instead of "spent" ones, which increases the cost of oil and gas production.

The proposed principle of cyclic development of shale HC deposits [4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 11, 14, 15] will significantly minimize the cost of drilling a large number of production wells, extend the life (operation) of already drilled wells and reduce the CAPEX in general (Fig. 8-9).

Each deposit (of traditional or non-traditional hydrocarbons) is unique by characteristics, and the development should be based on a well-chosen individual operating mode. For renewable deposits, development approaches are characterized by some common features.

Hydrocarbon deposit is a "living" system that is in hydrodynamic equilibrium before the start of production. The exploitation of the deposit disrupts the established equilibrium in the reservoir, stimulating a natural influx of hydrocarbon fluids, which begin to compensate for the amount of extraction. If, at the same time, the production rate (i.e. forced extraction) is several times higher than the rate of natural replenishment, then the deposit is temporarily depleted.

Figure 8. A graph of the cyclic shale development (V.A. Bochkarev [4, 5, 10, 14, 15, 18])

Thus, when exploiting a deposit, intensive HC production technologies (forced extraction, which is exactly what is observed in most deposits of the world) should be abandoned. It is necessary to be guided by the principle of "sparing" development; the development of renewable natural resources should be based on a balance of hydrocarbon generation volumes from SR and economically viable HC production rates. During the development planning, rehabilitation periods should be provided that will ensure the restoration of the energy potential of HC renewable systems.

For example, the long period of development of oil fields in the Middle East is explained (in addition to the huge oil reserves) mainly by the low (gentle) withdrawal rate.

Another example is one of the largest fields in the USA, East Texas, discovered in 1930 and put into intensive production from the same year. American experts plan to exploit it until 2030. It should be noted that the main reservoir of the field (Woodbine formation) is quite homogeneous with a permeability of 2.62 mkm², containing low-viscosity (0.93 MPa*s) oil, drilled with a very dense initial grid of wells and is being developed with a wide system of structured injection [24].

In Russia, especially in Western Siberia, the widespread use of various methods of increasing oil recovery (including widespread hydraulic fracturing) prevails. These methods are optimal in conditions of accelerated development of oil fields, but at the same time impact to their rapid depletion (like for example Verkhny Tarskoye field (Novosibirsk Region) [20].

Extended and intense disturbance of the reservoir system destroys the natural equilibrium, resulting in a rapid drop in formation pressure, a sharp decrease in flow rate, reservoir flooding, etc. N.P. Zapivalov and I.P. Popov in their work [20] note that the threshold disturbance to the system can be estimated through reservoir depression, which – as established for many deposits, it should not exceed 5 MPa.

Compliance with the critical threshold of reservoir depression (about 5 MPa), rehabilitation periods (periods of "natural refueling") and gentle individual methods of RF increasing, limiting water injection volumes (so as not to limit the flow of new portions of hydrocarbons into the reservoir) are necessary conditions for long-term and effective development of oil and gas fields due to the independent restoration of the natural systems.

Figure 9. The principle scheme of cyclic shale development [15].

From the very beginning of field development, it is necessary to provide for periodic work on geofluidodynamic monitoring and temporary production stops in order to ensure the restoration of hydrocarbon reserves due to "natural refueling". This will make it possible to preserve active HC reserves for a long period, the replenishment of which is possible due to newly formed volumes of hydrocarbons and gentle methods of increasing oil recovery that do not worsen the properties of productive formations.

Conclusions:

1. Facts are gradually accumulating (replenishment of reserves of long-exploited deposits, inconsistency of the duration of field production with estimated reserves, pulsating well flow rates), which indicate modern processes of oil and gas formation and replenishment of deposits with new portions of hydrocarbons.

2. The established facts of the replenishment of oil and gas reserves in the fields under development, along with other noted evidence, indicate that the processes of generation, migration of oil and gas and formation (reformation) of HC deposits occur much faster than previously thought - within several years, and sometimes even in a matter of months and weeks.

3. Fragile hydrocarbon systems are distinguished (located far from HC generation sources and have lost their hydrodynamic connection with them as a result of tectonic processes) and antifragile (using the potential of nearby large HC generation sources during development). Then closer the deposit to the HC generation zone, the faster the processes of its replenishment are going on.

4. The most obvious and representative examples of HC replenishment phenomenon are the HC deposits of Tatarstan (Romashkinskoye), Western Siberia (Salymskoye), Chechnya (Starogroznenskoye, Oktyabrskoye), Azerbaijan (Zykh, Shah Deniz), Iran (South Pars), Qatar (North), USA (East Texas, the shelf of the Gulf of Mexico, Prado Bay), Vietnam (White Tiger), Nigeria (Bomu, Okan), the western and southern coastal parts of the Caspian Depression (Astrakhan, Krachaganak), the Indolo-Kuban trough (Anastasyevsko-Troitskoye, Maikopskoye) and others.

5. Among the basins with shale formations with a similar phenomenon, the basins of the USA, Russia (the Bazhenov formation of western Siberia and domanic deposits of the Volga-Ural and Timan-Pechersk NGP), Australia, Argentina, China and Mexico, are distinguished.

6. To assess the resource base of replenished deposits, a potential balance method is proposed [4], taking into account the total volume of the SR, TOC, type of generated HC (gradation of catagenesis), rock density, the parameter of HC output from the rock and the HC emigration coefficient.

7. Each replenished deposit should be considered as a complex hydrodynamic system capable of self-healing in a relatively short time, measured in years and even months and weeks, depending on the proximity to the source of HC generation.

8. The exploitation of the deposit disrupts the established equilibrium in the reservoir, stimulating a natural influx of hydrocarbon fluids, which begin to compensate for the amount of extraction. If, at the same time, the production rate (i.e. forced extraction) is several times higher than the rate of natural replenishment, then the deposit is temporarily depleted.

9. The development of renewable hydrocarbon deposits should be planned based on the balance of hydrocarbon generation volumes (potential balance) and the HC deposits replenishment rate. The optimal system for maintaining a balance between production rates and the natural replenishment of hydrocarbons for this type of field is the optimal flow rate, which ensures the stability of formation pressure near the initial level.

10. Compliance with the critical threshold of reservoir depression (about 5 MPa), rehabilitation periods (periods of "natural refueling") and gentle individual methods of RF increasing, limiting water injection volumes (so as not to limit the flow of new portions of hydrocarbons into the reservoir) are necessary conditions for long-term and effective development of oil and gas fields due to the independent restoration of the natural systems.

11. The principle of cyclic development of shale hydrocarbon deposits [4-5] will significantly minimize the cost of drilling a large number of production wells, extend the operation life of already drilled wells and reduce the CAPEX in general.

12. It is necessary to correct the methodology of Exploration of renewable deposits. At the exploration stage, the analysis of the replenishment of hydrocarbon deposits of prospects, based on regional data (basin modeling) and data by the first exploration and evaluation wells (including pilot production), will determine the most optimal approach to their further development and maximize accumulated production, the RF and increase the IRR and NPV of fields with renewable HC reserves.

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